

Game-Theoretic Power Allocation and Client Selection for Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning in IoMT

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Abstract—In recent years, the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) has significantly boosted the healthcare industry. Federated learning (FL) can enhance the utilization of patient data while protecting privacy. Despite the great potential of FL to enhance the architecture of IoMT, the need for effective interference management and the limited energy resources of IoMT devices make the integration of FL into IoMT environments particularly challenging. This study proposes an innovative framework to address these challenges by optimizing power allocation and client selection across participating IoMT devices in the FL process. By employing a Stackelberg game model, our approach orchestrates power allocation among IoMT devices to enhance communication efficiency while adhering to strict differential privacy (DP) standards. Regarding the availability of network state information, we propose non-uniform pricing and uniform pricing strategies, respectively. Then, we derive the optimal interference price and power for the IoMT devices using nonlinear programming and convex optimization. To tackle the issue of energy constraints in IoMT devices, we adopt Lyapunov optimization for adaptive client selection, ensuring sustainable device participation in the FL process over time. In addition, our approach integrates DP to protect patient data, carefully balancing between privacy and the accuracy of the learning model. Our extensive simulations demonstrate marked improvements in privacy preservation, communication efficiency, and energy management efficiency, highlighting the effectiveness of our proposed method over existing solutions.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), Differential Privacy, Game Theory, Client Selection, Resource Allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the rise of advanced technologies and the expansion of wireless connectivity, the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) has emerged as a critical component of modern healthcare systems [1]. This network connects a wide range of intelligent medical devices, from wearable fitness trackers to sophisticated diagnostic tools, enabling the seamless collection and transmission of health data. Such real-time data sharing

allows healthcare professionals to make swift and informed decisions, enhancing the quality of patient care. Furthermore, the IoMT has been instrumental in advancing patient monitoring, increasing the accuracy of diagnostics, and personalizing treatment approaches [2].

Machine learning (ML) has been gradually applied to the IoMT to optimize the use of extensive health data [3]. However, the traditional centralized ML approach necessitates sending all sensitive health data to a central server, increasing the risk of data breaches and causing delays in processing and response. Nowadays, smart medical devices are equipped with enhanced storage and computing capabilities and can process data on-site. This advancement has positioned federated learning (FL) as a key approach [4], [5]. Consider a patient being treated for COVID-19 in a hospital. During treatment, the patient undergoes diagnostic procedures across several departments, such as radiology, cardiology, and pathology. Each department's specialized medical equipment (e.g., X-ray machines in radiology, electrocardiographs in cardiology, and blood analyzers in pathology) collects unique data that reflects different aspects of the patient's condition. Each device within these departments independently trains a local model on its collected data, applying privacy-preserving techniques (e.g., adding noise) to safeguard patient information before transmitting model updates to a central server. The central server aggregates these updates to refine a global model, which is then redistributed to each device to continue local training. This process leverages the specialized data from each department to enhance the global model, improving its accuracy in COVID-19 diagnosis by integrating diverse, department-specific insights.

While FL is designed to preserve user privacy by processing sensitive data directly on medical devices, it remains susceptible to inference attacks in certain scenarios [6]. Such attacks involve advanced methods to scrutinize model updates, enabling attackers to deduce confidential details from the data, thereby risking patient privacy. Due to the exceptionally strict privacy requirements for medical information, it is critical to ensure that robust privacy protections can address sophisticated cybersecurity threats without compromising the integrity of the health data necessary for diagnosis. The task becomes more complex when data is shared among different organizations, amplifying the need for flexible and universally accepted privacy measures.

In addition, the integration of IoMT brings together a

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This work is partly supported by the Natural Science Foundation of Sichuan under Grant 25GJHZ009, National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) under Grant 62071105, and by Horizon EU Grant No. 101086159 and No. 101131117.

multitude of smart medical devices, thus generating a large amount of data. Therefore, it becomes crucial to develop straightforward communication resource allocation policies to effectively manage data flows, avoid network congestion and ensure timely updates of FL models [7]–[9]. This is particularly important for applications such as remote patient monitoring and real-time diagnostics, where any delays can adversely affect patient care. Managing communication resources in IoMT is challenging for a number of reasons. First, the widespread use of medical devices requires careful allocation of the limited available communication resources. Second, these devices have different functionalities and channel conditions, making optimizing resource allocation a complex task. Moreover, when IoMT networks operate within public communication networks, various types of interference can arise [10], [11]. Cross-tier interference occurs when IoMT devices upload model updates to the server in the FL network while other users of the access point (AP) simultaneously transmit data over the same spectrum [12]. The cumulative interference at the AP not only affects the AP’s ability to handle its designated tasks but also reduces the overall system communication efficiency, leading to delays in the transmission of medical data and degradation of system performance. Managing such cross-tier interference is particularly challenging because IoMT devices typically lack the capability to autonomously regulate their transmission power. This necessitates the design of an external interference management framework to dynamically coordinate power control, mitigate interference, and ensure reliable data transmission in resource-constrained IoMT environments.

In this paper, we employ an integrated strategy to address the aforementioned challenges in IoMT. We protect patient privacy by implementing differential privacy (DP) mechanisms. Our DP mechanisms are designed to reduce the risk of privacy leakage by adding controlled noise, ensuring that individual patient information remains protected when faced with complex inference attacks. This approach provides measurable privacy guarantees, meeting the strict privacy requirements for medical data without compromising diagnostic accuracy. Furthermore, to mitigate the cross-tier interference in IoMT environments, we propose an AP-driven interference-aware communication framework that dynamically manages transmission power and reduces cumulative interference, thereby ensuring efficient and reliable communication within the system. Finally, we address the energy constraints faced by IoMT devices. To this end, we propose a strategy for the long-term selection of FL clients, with a careful trade-off between energy usage and learning efficiency, to promote continuous device engagement. Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

- In this work, we analyze the effects of channel noise and privacy noise on local and global gradients during FL transmission. Through this comprehensive analysis, we establish inequality constraints to achieve successful FL transmission while maintaining DP. Within the FL IoMT framework, these constraints are thoughtfully incorporated into the client’s utility function.

- Recognizing the limitations of medical devices in terms of environment awareness and power adaptation, we introduce an AP-driven interference management mechanism. The AP sets interference power constraints and uses pricing strategies to incentivize IoMT devices to optimize their transmission power. By formulating the problem as a Stackelberg game, we derive the optimal interference price and power allocation through nonlinear programming and convex optimization. To adapt to varying levels of network state information, we further propose non-uniform and uniform pricing schemes to achieve efficient communication resource allocation in IoMT networks.
- To manage the energy constraints of IoMT devices during FL training, we propose a strategic energy allocation approach. By leveraging Lyapunov optimization, we create a virtual queue to monitor energy deficits and help select clients. This process is complemented by a power allocation strategy derived from the Stackelberg game and applied throughout the FL training process. Our approach strikes a balance between client selection, power allocation, and long-term energy management. This ensures that device participation in FL networks is both effective and energy efficient.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we provide a review of the literature in related research areas. In Section III, we present the system model for FL-assisted IoMT, including the communication model and the privacy model. Section IV proposes a power allocation scheme based on the Stackelberg game. Section V presents the FL client selection and power allocation scheme under long-term consideration. Section VI presents experimental results to verify the effectiveness of the proposed scheme. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In recent years, FL has seen extensive application across various IoMT domains, including the management of electronic healthcare records (EHRs), remote health monitoring, medical imaging, and COVID-19 analysis and detection [13]–[20]. For instance, [13] explored a blockchain-based FL approach to enhance the security and privacy of EHRs in healthcare settings. [14] introduced a personalized FL model that leverages tensor data fusion to identify impairments in structural health monitoring, aiming to overcome the limitations associated with centralized and decentralized learning models. [15]–[17] examined FL’s role in medical imaging, focusing on strategies to accommodate intermittent clients, manage unbalanced data within intelligent healthcare systems, safeguard data privacy, and bolster model performance and robustness. Moreover, [18]–[20] underscored FL’s significant contributions to public health through COVID-19 analysis and detection, highlighting its potential to facilitate advancements in the field.

Numerous studies have focused on bolstering privacy preservation in FL for the IoMT, employing various techniques such as secure multi-party computation (SMPC), DP, Veri-fyNet, and adversarial training. [21] developed an FL framework tailored for IoMT in 6G networks that enhances both

data privacy and model accuracy using SMPC. [22] introduced RFLPV, a robust FL scheme with privacy preservation and verifiable aggregation for managing heterogeneous medical data. Furthermore, [23] explored federated adversarial learning to enhance both the robustness and privacy of models for biomedical named entity recognition.

The application of game theory to FL in the IoMT has led to innovative approaches for encouraging client participation and optimizing resource allocation. Techniques such as Stackelberg game, auction, and contract theory have been pivotal in this context. [7] utilized the Stackelberg game model to address the strategic dynamics between FL networks and potential jammers within the IoMT ecosystem, aiming to enhance the networks' resilience to jamming while ensuring efficient learning and communication. [24], [25] employed a similar Stackelberg game framework to navigate the complex interactions between mobile edge computing (MEC) servers and clients engaged in collaborative learning, optimizing power and privacy settings to achieve a balance between utility maximization, energy efficiency, and privacy preservation. [26] introduced an auction-based mechanism to motivate mobile users to share their data for FL, thereby enhancing model performance and promoting social welfare. At the same time, [27] employed contract theory to encourage the participation of data holders with large amounts of data and computational resources, thus improving the quality of the global model. These studies highlight the versatility and effectiveness of game-theoretic approaches in advancing the FL domain, especially in optimizing interactions and incentives within the IoMT framework.

Moreover, the challenge of client selection in FL has been tackled through various methodologies, including clustering by [28], greedy selection techniques by [29], multi-armed bandit (MAB) based approaches by [30] and random selection strategies by [31]. These studies introduce diverse strategies to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of participant selection in FL. However, a common limitation among these approaches is their focus on optimizing each FL round in isolation, leading to a uniform allocation of network resources across all learning iterations.

However, previous studies overlook the integration of long-term resource allocation and client selection in FL IoMT system with a focus on privacy. Our research addresses this gap by applying DP to FL in IoMT. We use a game-theoretic method for power allocation to maximize communication efficiency within DP guarantee. Moreover, we assess the varying importance of FL rounds and explore strategies for long-term power allocation and client selection, considering energy constraints. This approach ensures both privacy protection and efficient resource use over time.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model for our FL framework in the IoMT is shown in Fig. 1. We consider a cross-device FL training process that involves medical devices in various departments of a large hospital, which form a traditional star topology [32]. (Note: Throughout this paper, the terms clients, IoMT devices, and client devices are used interchangeably to refer to the entities

TABLE I
TABLE OF NOTATION

Notation	Definition
λ_i	payoff factors
h_i	channel gain between client i and server
g_i	channel gain between client i and AP
N	number of clients
β	upper bound on the sum of interference from other clients
σ^2	background noise
B	channel bandwidth
τ_i	the fraction of power dedicated to artificial noise
N_0	channel noise
δ	DP parameter
T	learning iteration
Λ	the size of network model
p^{max}	the maximum transmission power of the devices
\mathbf{w}	global model parameters
η_t	learning rate at iteration t
\mathbf{x}_i^t	transmitted signal from client i at iteration t
m_i^t	standard deviation of effective noise
$SINR_i$	signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio for client i
r_i	uplink rate of client i
p_i	transmission power of client i
μ_i	interference price for client i
$\zeta_i(t)$	binary variable indicating client i 's participation in round t
ρ_i	priority metric for client selection
$q_i(t)$	virtual queue length of client i at round t
E_i^{max}	maximal energy budget of client i
$\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)$	local gradient of client i
\mathbf{z}	channel noise

participating as clients in the FL process.) Here, medical sensors on client devices collect health and environmental data. This data supports the local training of ML models directly on the devices, enhancing computation efficiency. The models' updates, mainly gradients, are then transmitted to a central server. To ensure the privacy of this sensitive data, we incorporate DP mechanisms into the transmission process. Continuous gradient transmission places high demands on the AP, which can lead to network interference and reduced efficiency. In the system model, the AP is responsible for managing the transmission of local updates from numerous clients. The performance of the AP is critical to the stability and efficiency of the network.

A. Federated Learning Model

In our FL framework, a server collaborates with a set \mathcal{N} of N clients to analyze healthcare data. Each client i possesses a private dataset \mathcal{D}_i , comprising $|\mathcal{D}_i|$ data points, where each point is represented as a pair $(\mathbf{u}_j^{(i)}, v_j^{(i)})$. Here, $\mathbf{u}_j^{(i)}$ indicates the j -th data point, and $v_j^{(i)}$ its corresponding label for client i . The goal is to collaboratively train a model by minimizing the loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$, defined as:

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} F(\mathbf{w}) \triangleq \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_{\text{total}}|} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{D}_i|} f_i((\mathbf{u}_j^{(i)}, v_j^{(i)}); \mathbf{w}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the parameter vector, $f_i(\cdot)$ is the loss function for client i , and $\mathcal{D}_{\text{total}} = \cup_{i=1}^N \mathcal{D}_i$ is the aggregated dataset.

FL training is executed iteratively across T iterations via distributed gradient descent. At each iteration t , the server

Fig. 1. Interference-aware and privacy-preserving FL system in IoMT.

sends the current global parameter vector \mathbf{w}^t to all clients. Each client i calculates its local gradient over its dataset, $\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \nabla f_i(\mathbf{u}_j^{(i)}, v_j^{(i)}; \mathbf{w}^t)$, and returns this gradient to the server. The global parameters are updated as follows:

$$\mathbf{w}^{t+1} = \mathbf{w}^t - \eta \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t), \quad (2)$$

where η represents the learning rate. This process repeats until the model converges.

B. Communication Model for Federated Learning

To ensure consistency in signal strength and privacy preservation in wireless transmissions, we use a similar approach to [33], i.e., we incorporate power into the scaling factor of the signal. At each training iteration t , a client device i transmits its computed gradient vector \mathbf{x}_i^t , which consists of two parts: the local gradient estimate and local perturbation for privacy. This is mathematically represented as:

$$\mathbf{x}_i^t = \underbrace{\frac{\sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}}{\Lambda} \nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)}_{\text{local gradient estimate}} + \underbrace{\sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t} \mathbf{n}_i^t}_{\text{local perturbation}}, \quad (3)$$

where the gradient vector is normalized by Λ , and the power fractions θ_i and τ_i are allocated to the gradient vector and the Gaussian noise $\mathbf{n}_i^t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, respectively. These fractions are constrained such that $\theta_i + \tau_i \leq 1$.

At iteration t , the signal sent by client i arrives at the server containing the transmitted signal and channel noise. Given that the hospital environment we consider is an indoor setting, the signal propagation adheres to the characteristics typical of indoor wireless communication environments. Therefore, we adopt the log-distance path loss model, which is widely used in indoor signal propagation studies due to its ability to accurately represent large-scale path loss caused by physical obstructions such as walls, floors, and medical equipment [34]. Under this assumption, the channel gain h_i between client i

and the server in our model is primarily influenced by the distance between client i and the server. The channel noise is Gaussian-distributed, following $\mathcal{N}(0, N_0 \mathbf{I})$.

Considering the transmitted and received signals, the effective noise in the system combines both channel noise and the injected noise, with its standard deviation being:

$$m_i^t = \sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t})^2 + N_0}. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the server can obtain local gradients with noise by processing the received signals. The local gradient with noise of client i is

$$\widehat{\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)} = \nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t) + (h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t} \mathbf{n}_i + N_0) \cdot \frac{\Lambda}{h_i \sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}} \quad (5)$$

Aggregating these noise-adjusted local gradients from all clients results in the global gradient with noise:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \widehat{\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)} \\ &= \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t} \mathbf{n}_i + N_0 \right) \cdot \frac{\Lambda}{h_i \sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) for client i during transmission is:

$$SINR_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) = \frac{p_i h_i}{\sum_{j \neq i} p_j h_j + \sigma^2}, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \quad (7)$$

where p_i the transmission power of client i , σ^2 the background noise, and \mathbf{p}_{-i} the power allocation for all other clients. This formula is the basis for the uplink rate r_i and is critical for efficient gradient transmission:

$$r_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) = B \log_2(1 + SINR_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i})), \quad (8)$$

with B representing the channel bandwidth.

For successful training in FL, clients must transmit their gradients $\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)$ efficiently. We set a threshold $\Lambda = |\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)|_b$, where b specifies the buffer bit rate, ensuring the

integrity of gradient information. It is imperative for the uplink rate r_i to meet or exceed this threshold in every iteration for the training to proceed effectively:

$$r_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) \geq \Lambda. \quad (9)$$

C. Differential Privacy Analysis

1) *Definition of DP*: DP aims to protect individual privacy within a dataset. To illustrate, consider a healthcare scenario involving a binary classification task to predict whether an individual has a specific medical condition, based on features like age and blood pressure. Imagine two adjacent datasets: \mathcal{D}' , which excludes an individual named Alice, and \mathcal{D}'' , which includes Alice's data. Our objective is to train a model to predict the likelihood of having the medical condition while preserving Alice's privacy. For this scenario, DP loss $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}''}(\mathbf{y})$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}''}(\mathbf{y}) = \ln \frac{P(\mathbf{y}|\mathcal{D}')}{P(\mathbf{y}|\mathcal{D}'')} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{y} represents the model's output. For instance, if $P(\mathbf{y}|\mathcal{D}') = 0.8$ and $P(\mathbf{y}|\mathcal{D}'') = 0.6$, then $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}''}(\mathbf{y}) \approx 0.2877$.

This DP loss quantifies the change in model output due to the inclusion or exclusion of Alice's data, expressed as a logarithmic ratio. To satisfy the DP criterion, the absolute value of this loss must remain within the range defined by the parameters ϵ and δ .

Definition 1. A randomized mechanism $\mathcal{A} : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$ with domain \mathcal{X} and range \mathcal{R} satisfies (ϵ, δ) -DP [35] if for any two adjacent datasets $\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}'' \in \mathcal{X}$ and for all measurable sets $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$,

$$\Pr[\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{D}') \in \mathcal{S}] \leq e^\epsilon \Pr[\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{D}'') \in \mathcal{S}] + \delta, \quad (11)$$

where ϵ is the privacy budget and δ is the probability that (ϵ, δ) -DP is broken.

This framework ensures that the presence or absence of any single individual's data (like Alice's) has a limited impact on the output, thereby protecting privacy. The (ϵ, δ) -DP condition aims to keep the DP loss under a small threshold ϵ with high probability $1 - \delta$, i.e., $\Pr(|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}', \mathcal{D}''}(\mathbf{y})| \leq \epsilon) \geq 1 - \delta$, making re-identification of individual data statistically challenging for the adversary.

2) *DP Guarantee*: Considering Definition 1 and the whole transmission process comprehensively, the following lemma can be obtained.

Lemma 1. DP guarantee. For a given p_i , the FL gradient aggregation process can ensure (ϵ, δ) -DP if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}h_i\sqrt{\tau_i}\Lambda}{\sqrt{(h_i\sqrt{\tau_i}p_i)^2 + N_0}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta)}{T} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}} \triangleq \left(\sqrt{\epsilon + [\mathcal{C}^{-1}(1/\delta)]^2} - \mathcal{C}^{-1}(1/\delta) \right)^2$, and \mathcal{C}^{-1} is the inverse function of $\mathcal{C}(x) = \sqrt{\pi}xe^{x^2}$.

Proof. See Appendix A for details. \square

The DP guarantee in Lemma 1 plays a pivotal role in our framework by ensuring that the FL process in IoMT adheres to strict privacy standards. This theoretical foundation supports the practical implementation of our privacy-preserving FL model. Consequently, the successful transmission requirement of FL in (9) and the DP guarantee in (12) will be taken into account together as constraints in the later problem.

D. FL Convergence Analysis

Before performing the convergence analysis, we make the following assumptions about the loss function, as in [36].

Assumption 1. Smoothness: The global loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$ is smooth with constant $L > 0$. This implies that $F(\mathbf{w})$ is continuously differentiable and that its gradient $\nabla F(\mathbf{w})$ is Lipschitz continuous with a constant L . Mathematically expressed as:

$$\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}) - \nabla F(\mathbf{w}')\| \leq L\|\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{w}'\|, \quad \forall \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}'.$$

This leads to the following inequality:

$$F(\mathbf{w}') \leq F(\mathbf{w}) + \nabla F(\mathbf{w})^\top (\mathbf{w}' - \mathbf{w}) + \frac{L}{2} \|\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{w}'\|^2, \quad \forall \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}'.$$

Assumption 2. Polyak-Lojasiewicz Inequality: Optimization problem (1) has a non-empty solution set. Let F^* be the value of the corresponding optimal function, and the global loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$ satisfies the Polyak-Lojasiewicz (PL) condition, i.e., the following inequality holds for some constant $\psi > 0$:

$$\frac{1}{2} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w})\|^2 \geq \psi[F(\mathbf{w}) - F^*].$$

Lemma 2. Under Assumption 1 and Assumption 2, the upper bound on the average optimality gap after T iterations for $\eta = 1/L$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[F(\mathbf{w}^{(T+1)}) - F^* \right] &\leq \left(1 - \frac{\psi}{L} \right)^T \left[F(\mathbf{w}^{(1)}) - F^* \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{2LN^2} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(1 - \frac{\psi}{L} \right)^{T-t} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{m_i^t}{h_i\sqrt{\tau_i}p_i^t} \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the standard deviation $m_k^{(t)}$ of the effective noise is defined in (4). The lemma demonstrates that even in the presence of noise, the algorithm can still converge at a certain rate to a region near the optimal value.

Proof. See Appendix B. \square

IV. GAME-BASED POWER ALLOCATION FOR FL

A. Stackelberg Game Formulation

In the context of resource allocation problems, the Stackelberg game is a hierarchical decision-making framework where players are divided into leaders and followers. In this type of game, the leader makes the first decision, which influences the responses of the followers. The objective of each player

is to optimize their respective utility functions based on these hierarchical interactions. This structure makes the Stackelberg game particularly suitable for scenarios where a central agent (the leader) has priority in decision-making, subsequently guiding the strategies of other agents (the followers). To further clarify our model, we provide definitions of key terms in the Stackelberg game model as they pertain to our scenario:

- **Leader:** The leader in a Stackelberg game makes the initial decision, influencing the strategies of the followers. In our model, the AP serves as the leader, setting the interference price to manage the power usage of IoMT devices.
- **Followers:** Followers are players who observe the leader's decision and choose their strategies accordingly. Here, the IoMT devices are the followers that adjust their transmission power based on the interference price set by the AP.
- **Utility Function:** In game theory, a utility function quantifies each player's preferences for different outcomes based on their strategies. In a Stackelberg game, both the leader and the followers have distinct utility functions that they aim to optimize. For the AP (leader), the utility function is designed to optimize network efficiency by balancing interference levels against the interference price. For the IoMT devices (followers), the utility function reflects a trade-off between transmission power and the interference cost imposed by the AP. The devices adjust their power levels to maximize their own utility, maintaining effective communication while minimizing interference costs.

1) *AP side:* In the IoMT ecosystem, reliable data transmission is crucial. Due to simultaneous device communication, the FL process generates extra interference at the AP, which leads to network congestion. To ensure its own quality of service (QoS), the AP sets the interference constraint C to ensure that the total interference from all clients does not exceed this threshold:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N I_i(p_i) \leq C, \quad (14)$$

where $I_i(p_i) \triangleq g_i p_i$ denotes the interference power from client i . Under the log-distance path loss model, the channel gain g_i , similar to h_i , is influenced by the distance between client i and the AP as well as obstructions in the indoor hospital environment.

The AP aims to maximize its utility by setting optimal prices for the interference quota purchased by each client:

$$U_{AP}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i I_i(p_i) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i g_i p_i, \quad (15)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_N]^T$ is the vector of interference prices, and $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N]^T$ denotes the clients' power levels.

Within the framework of our game, the amount of interference quota each client opts to buy is influenced by the pricing set by the AP. Given the AP's maximum interference capacity, it must strategically determine the optimal pricing

for interference to enhance its revenue. Therefore, the AP's objective function is defined to maximize this revenue by adjusting the interference prices accordingly:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} U_{AP}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{p}), \\ & \text{s.t. } \sum_{i=1}^N I_i(p_i) \leq C, \\ & \boldsymbol{\mu} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where \succeq indicates inequality relations between vectors.

2) *FL Network Side:* Each client's utility is a balance between the benefits of transmitting at higher power (improving uplink rate and consequently utility) and the costs associated with higher interference (requiring the purchase of more interference quota). Therefore, the utility of client i can be defined as

$$U_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}, \mu_i) = \lambda_i r_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) - \mu_i I_i(p_i), \quad (17)$$

where λ_i quantifies the utility gained per unit of uplink rate.

Clients aim to optimize their transmission power to maximize utility, considering both the cost of interference and the need to maintain communication efficiency and privacy standards. Therefore, clients solve the following optimization problem

$$\max_{p_i} U_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}, \boldsymbol{\mu}), \quad (18)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} \Lambda}{\sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} p_i)^2 + N_0}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{R}_{dp}(\epsilon, \delta)}{T}, \forall i, \quad (19)$$

$$r_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) \geq \Lambda, \forall i, \quad (20)$$

$$0 \leq p_i \leq p^{max}, \forall i, \quad (21)$$

where p^{max} is the maximum transmission power of the devices. Constraint (19) ensures (ϵ, δ) -DP and constraint (20) ensures the successful transmission of parameter gradients during FL training.

B. Stackelberg Equilibrium

Definition 2. Suppose that $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*$ solves (16) and \mathbf{p}^* solves (18). Then, for any pair $(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{p})$ (where $\boldsymbol{\mu} \succeq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{p} \succeq \mathbf{0}$), the combination $(\boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \mathbf{p}^*)$ forms an SE, if it satisfies the following definitions:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{AP}(\boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \mathbf{p}^*) & \geq U_{AP}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{p}^*), \\ U_i(p_i^*, \mathbf{p}_{-i}^*, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*) & \geq U_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}^*, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*), \forall i. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Remark. To identify the SE, it's essential to determine the subgame perfect Nash equilibrium (NE) for the game's components. In our scenario, IoMT clients engage in a non-cooperative game where they independently adjust their power levels to optimize utility, forming a non-cooperative power control subgame. A NE in this context means that no client can improve their utility by solely changing their strategy, given the strategies of others remain unchanged. For the AP, being the sole decision-maker in its domain, finding the optimal strategy is straightforward once the clients' responses are known. The process involves first solving for the clients' best response strategies to any given interference price $\boldsymbol{\mu}$, thus

addressing the non-cooperative game among IoMT clients. Subsequently, leveraging the derived optimal power allocations \mathbf{p}^* , the AP calculates the optimal interference prices $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*$ to maximize its revenue, thereby achieving the SE.

Next, we will consider two pricing methods, non-uniform and uniform pricing. We will compare these two pricing methods, explaining their advantages and disadvantages as well as the scenarios where they are applicable.

C. Non-Uniform Pricing

In the context of non-uniform pricing, the AP assigns varied interference prices to distinct clients within FL networks. Then, (18) is transformed into the following form

$$\max_{p_i} \lambda_i B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_i h_i}{\sum_{j \neq i} p_j h_j + \sigma^2} \right) - \mu_i g_i p_i, \quad (23)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} \Lambda}{\sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} p_i)^2 + N_0}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta)}{T}, \quad (24)$$

$$B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_i h_i}{\sum_{j \neq i} p_j h_j + \sigma^2} \right) \geq |\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)| b, \quad (25)$$

$$0 \leq p_i \leq p^{\text{max}}, \quad (26)$$

where we can express the first two constraints in the following form:

$$p_i \geq \frac{2\Lambda^2 T}{\mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta)} - \frac{N_0}{h_i^2 \tau_i} \triangleq A_i^{\text{dp}}, \quad (27)$$

$$p_i \geq \frac{\left(2^{\frac{|\nabla F_i(\mathbf{w}^t)| b}{B}} - 1 \right) \left(\sum_{j \neq i} p_j h_j + \sigma^2 \right)}{h_i} \triangleq A_i^{\text{suc}}, \quad (28)$$

and let $A_i = \max\{A_i^{\text{dp}}, A_i^{\text{suc}}\}$.

To derive a closed-form solution for the variable p_i , we begin by taking the first-order derivative of the objective function, resulting in an expression for the optimal power level \hat{p}_i :

$$\hat{p}_i = \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i g_i} - \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j + \sigma^2}{h_i}. \quad (29)$$

We introduce an assumption that limits the total interference received by client i from other clients to an upper bound β , simplifying the notation and analysis throughout the paper. This upper bound β effectively replaces $\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j$ in our calculations. The assumption is valid for the following reasons [37]. Firstly, the channel gain between devices is typically very weak due to penetration loss. This implies that even if multiple devices transmit signals simultaneously, the resulting superimposed interference is still significantly limited by physical constraints, thereby ensuring that the total interference remains manageable. Secondly, the peak transmit power of each IoMT device is typically constrained by regulatory limits [38]. These regulations ensure that even in the worst-case scenario, the interference from any individual device remains low, thereby keeping the total interference within a manageable range.

For client i to effectively participate in the FL process, it is critical that the chosen power level \hat{p}_i meets the privacy preservation requirements while ensuring the successful transmission of the parameter gradient. The optimal power allocation for client i incorporates these considerations as follows.

Lemma 3. The optimal solution for power allocation of client i is:

$$p_i^* = \begin{cases} \hat{p}_i, & \text{if } \hat{p}_i \geq A_i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Substituting (30) into (16), the utility function at the AP becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i g_i p_i^*(\mu_i), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N g_i p_i^*(\mu_i) \leq C, \\ & \boldsymbol{\mu} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Assuming the interference capacity C is adequately large and the AP sets the interference prices such that $\mu_i \leq \frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i (h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}$, we can reformulate the original problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\lambda_i B - \frac{\mu_i g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} - \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right) \leq C, \\ & \boldsymbol{\mu} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \\ & \mu_i \leq \frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i (h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}, \forall i. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The problem can be transformed into the form of minimizing the objective function as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\mu_i g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} \leq C + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}, \\ & \boldsymbol{\mu} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \\ & \mu_i \leq \frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i (h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}, \forall i. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Proposition 1. The solution to the problem (33) is:

$$\mu_i^* = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{C + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}, \forall i. \quad (34)$$

Proof. It is easy to observe that the problem (33) is convex and hence we use the Lagrangian method to solve the problem.

Next, we construct the Lagrangian function J , where the Lagrangian multipliers $\nu \geq 0$ and $\xi_i \geq 0$ correspond to the two constraints of the problem, respectively:

$$J(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \nu, \boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\mu_i g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} + \nu \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} - C - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right) - \sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i \mu_i. \quad (35)$$

Now we take the partial derivative of J with respect to each μ_i and set the result to zero. In this way, according to the KKT condition we get:

$$\frac{\partial J(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \nu, \boldsymbol{\xi})}{\partial \mu_i} = 0, \forall i, \quad (36)$$

$$\nu \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} - C - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right) = 0, \quad (37)$$

$$\nu \geq 0, \xi_i \geq 0, \mu_i \geq 0, \xi_i \mu_i = 0, \forall i, \quad (38)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} - C - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \leq 0. \quad (39)$$

From (36), we have

$$\mu_i^2 = \frac{\nu \lambda_i B}{\frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} - \xi_i}. \quad (40)$$

To satisfy the KKT condition, we have

$$\xi_i = 0, \quad (41)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu_i} - C - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} = 0. \quad (42)$$

Joining (40) and (42), we have

$$\mu_i = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{C + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}, \forall i. \quad (43)$$

□

Proposition 2. The interference prices given by (34) are the optimal solutions to the problem (31) if $C \geq$

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{\min_i \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}}} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}.$$

Proof. By (34), we have obtained an optimal solution to problem (33). In order to satisfy the assumption $\mu_i \leq \frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}$, we substitute (34), and we get:

$$\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{C + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}} \leq \frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)} \quad (44)$$

Thus, it follows that

$$C \geq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}}} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}, \forall i. \quad (45)$$

The equation can be abbreviated as:

$$C \geq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{\min_i \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}}} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}. \quad (46)$$

□

Theorem 1. Assuming all clients are sorted in descending order according to $\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 B h_1}{g_1} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_1 A_1 + \beta + \sigma^2)}} > \dots > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{N-1} B h_{N-1}}{g_{N-1}} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_{N-1} A_{N-1} + \beta + \sigma^2)}} > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_N B h_N}{g_N} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_N A_N + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$, then the optimal solution to problem (31) can be given by the following formula:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}^* = \begin{cases} c_N \left[\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 h_1}{g_1(\beta + \sigma^2)}}, \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_2 h_2}{g_2(\beta + \sigma^2)}}, \dots, \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_N h_N}{g_N(\beta + \sigma^2)}} \right]^T, & \text{if } C > C_N \\ c_{N-1} \left[\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 h_1}{g_1(\beta + \sigma^2)}}, \dots, \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{N-1} h_{N-1}}{g_{N-1}(\beta + \sigma^2)}} \right]^T, & \text{if } C_N \geq C > C_{N-1} \\ \vdots \\ c_1 \left[\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 h_1}{g_1(\beta + \sigma^2)}}, \infty, \dots, \infty \right]^T, & \text{if } C_2 \geq C > C_1 \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

where $c_K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{C + \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}$ and $C_K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_K B h_K}{g_K} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_K A_K + \beta + \sigma^2)}}} - \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{g_i(\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}$, $\forall K \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$.

Proof. If $C > C_N$, then according to Proposition 2, the optimal solution $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*$ can be obtained. For other intervals such as $C_N > C > C_{N-1}$, the optimal solution $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*$ can also be derived based on Proposition 2. Therefore, Theorem 1 is proven. □

Remark. This theorem holds significant implications for the FL system within the IoMT. For instance, if the AP assigns an infinite optimal interference price μ_i^* to a specific client i , it effectively excludes that client from participating in the FL training. To ensure participation from all N clients, the AP must set its interference tolerance threshold above a critical value, C_N . This mechanism facilitates strategic client selection within the FL framework.

Thus, for the non-uniform pricing process, the SE ($\boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \boldsymbol{p}^*$) between the AP and IoMT clients is given by (47) and (30).

Algorithm 1 outlines the process for allocating power and setting interference prices under a non-uniform pricing model, centrally managed by the AP. The procedure begins with the AP gathering essential network data through the communication link. This data includes channel gains for each IoMT client, alongside privacy parameters and model details related to FL training. Leveraging this information and Theorem 1, the AP calculates a series of threshold values, encapsulated within the vector $\boldsymbol{C} = [C_N, C_{N-1}, \dots, C_1]^T$. These thresholds are instrumental in defining the interference prices for IoMT

Algorithm 1 Centralized Power Allocation and Interference Pricing under Non-Uniform Pricing

- 1: Set $K = N$.
- 2: Sort the K clients according to $\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B h_i}{g_i} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_i A_i + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$ (i.e., $\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 B h_1}{g_1} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_1 A_1 + \beta + \sigma^2)}} > \dots > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_K B h_K}{g_K} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_K A_K + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$).
- 3: Compute $c_K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{C + \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}$.
- 4: Comparing the c_K with $\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_K B h_K}{g_K} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_K A_K + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$. If $c_K > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_K B h_K}{g_K} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_K A_K + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$, remove client K from the game, set $K = K - 1$, and go to step 3; otherwise, go to step 5.
- 5: With c_K and K , the interference price μ_i for client i is given by

$$\mu_i = \begin{cases} c_K \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i h_i}{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}}, & \text{if } i \leq K \\ \infty, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

- 6: **return** *SelectedClients*, μ , \mathbf{p}
-

clients, who, upon receiving this pricing information, adjust their power to align with the new costs.

The complexity of Algorithm 1 primarily consists of several parts. Lines 1, 5 and 6 are constant time operations. Line 2 sorts the K clients, with a complexity of $O(K \log K)$. Line 3 computes c_K with a complexity of $O(K)$. Line 4 involves comparison and update operations, which, in the worst case, may require N iterations, each with a complexity of $O(K)$, resulting in a total complexity of $O(NK)$. Lines 5 and 6 are constant time operations. In summary, the total time complexity of Algorithm 1 is $O(NK)$. Since initially K is set to N , the total time complexity can be simplified to $O(N^2)$.

One noteworthy aspect is that the adoption of such algorithms may impose considerable computational and communication burdens. These burdens arise from the large amount of information gathering required by each client and the personalized computation of interference prices. To mitigate these challenges, we recommend transitioning to a uniform pricing strategy in subsequent sections. This strategy simplifies the task of the AP to simply tracking the total interference power received from all IoMT clients, i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^N I_i(p_i)$. This simplification not only reduces computational requirements, but also improves overall network efficiency by minimizing operational overhead.

D. Uniform Pricing

In this section, the AP imposes a uniform interference pricing of $\mu_i = \mu$, $\forall i$, for all IoMT clients. After receiving the uniform price, the IoMT clients can calculate their respective optimal transmit power using (30).

$$p_i^* = \begin{cases} \hat{p}_i, & \text{if } \hat{p}_i \geq A_i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (48)$$

where

$$\hat{p}_i = \frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu g_i} - \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j + \sigma^2}{h_i}. \quad (49)$$

Algorithm 2 Distributed Interference Price Bargaining under Uniform Pricing

- 1: AP initializes interference price μ and broadcasts to all clients, threshold C and tolerance ε , step size $\Delta\mu > 0$
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: **for** each client $i = 1$ to N **do**
 - 4: Compute optimal transmit power p_i^* based on received μ
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: AP measures total interference $I_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^N I_i(p_i)$
 - 7: **if** $I_{\text{total}} > C + \varepsilon$ **then**
 - 8: Increase μ by $\Delta\mu$
 - 9: **else if** $I_{\text{total}} < C - \varepsilon$ **then**
 - 10: Decrease μ by $\Delta\mu$
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: AP broadcasts new interference price μ to all clients
 - 13: **until** $|I_{\text{total}} - C| \leq \varepsilon$
 - 14: **return** *SelectedClients*, μ , \mathbf{p}
-

On the AP side, the structure of the optimization problem is similar to (31), and the problem form is simplified as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mu} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\lambda_i B - \frac{\mu g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\lambda_i B}{\mu} - \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i} \right) \leq C, \\ & \mu > 0. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Based on Theorem 1, the following corollary can be derived:

Corollary 1. Assuming all clients are sorted in descending order according to $\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 B h_1}{g_1} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_1 A_1 + \beta + \sigma^2)}} > \dots > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{N-1} B h_{N-1}}{g_{N-1}} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_{N-1} A_{N-1} + \beta + \sigma^2)}} > \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_N B h_N}{g_N} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_N A_N + \beta + \sigma^2)}}$, then the optimal solution to problem (50) can be given by the following formula:

$$\mu^* = \begin{cases} \tilde{\mu}_N, & \text{if } C > \tilde{C}_N \\ \tilde{\mu}_{N-1}, & \text{if } \tilde{C}_N \geq C > \tilde{C}_{N-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{\mu}_1, & \text{if } \tilde{C}_2 \geq C > \tilde{C}_1, \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

where $\tilde{\mu}_K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \lambda_i B}{C + \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}$ and $\tilde{C}_K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i B g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_K B h_K}{g_K} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_K A_K + \beta + \sigma^2)}}} - \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{g_i (\beta + \sigma^2)}{h_i}$, $\forall K \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$.

Corollary 2. The SE for uniform pricing is (μ^*, \mathbf{p}^*) , which is obtained respectively by (51) and (48).

Like non-uniform pricing methods, uniform pricing can be centralized. However, it requires the AP to collect a large amount of information from each IoMT device, which can be very complex. Nevertheless, as shown in (50), the problem formulated for uniform pricing has characteristics that are favorable for algorithmic exploitation. Specifically,

both the objective function and the first constraint exhibit monotonically decreasing with respect to the uniform price μ . This feature implies that the objective function reaches its maximum value when the constraints are fully satisfied. Taking advantage of this observation, we introduce the algorithm 2, which is a distributed bargaining algorithm designed to determine the equilibrium disturbance price in a uniform pricing framework. Unlike centralized approaches, this distributed approach eliminates the need to collect and process detailed information about each device, thus providing a more practical solution for interference price determination.

In Algorithm 2, the AP first sets an initial interference price and then passes it to the IoMT devices. Based on the initial price, each device calculates and sets its transmit power. Subsequently, the AP summarizes the interference generated by all devices and iteratively adjusts the interference price to keep the total interference within a predetermined threshold. This iterative process continues until the total interference stabilizes at a predetermined precise level. The use of a uniform pricing model greatly reduces the information burden on the AP in terms of price adjustment and contributes to a smoother realization of SE.

The complexity of Algorithm 2 is as follows. The complexity of each iteration from line 2 to line 13 is $O(N)$. Assuming the algorithm runs for T_1 iterations to meet the stopping criterion, the total time complexity is $O(T_1N)$, indicating that the algorithm's runtime scales linearly with both the number of clients N and the number of iterations T_1 .

E. Non-Uniform Pricing vs. Uniform Pricing

In the following, we compare these two pricing methods and present the advantages and applicable scenarios.

The non-uniform pricing strategy is the preferred choice in situations where network state information (e.g., channel gains of individual links, etc.) can be directly accessed. This is because:

- *Allows for differentiated management:* Non-uniform pricing enables different interference prices to be set for each IoMT client based on their specific level of interference to the AP. This differentiated pricing strategy allows for more fine-grained management of interference.
- *Revenue Maximization:* By setting different prices for different interference levels, the AP can get higher revenue from the most interfering users, thus maximizing the revenue of the whole network.
- *Resource allocation efficiency:* The AP are able to dynamically adjust prices based on the real-time status of the network as a feedback to regulate the transmission power of users, thereby optimizing the allocation of network resources.

When there is a lack of accurate network status information, or when the cost of obtaining such information is too high, uniform pricing becomes a more practical option. Advantages of uniform pricing in this case include:

- *Simplicity of implementation:* The lack of need for exhaustive network status information reduces the need for

Algorithm 3 Client Selection, Power Allocation, and Interference Pricing Algorithm Based on Long-Term Energy Constraints in IoMT

- 1: **Input:** $q_i(0) = 0, \forall i$
 - 2: Observe the channel state h_i
 - 3: Rank the clients according to ρ_i . Hence we have $\rho_1 \leq \rho_2 \leq \dots \leq \rho_N$
 - 4: Initialize the final selected set of clients S to \emptyset
 - 5: **for** $i = |S| + 1, \dots, N$ **do**
 - 6: Update S by adding client i
 - 7: Applying Algorithm 1 or Algorithm 2 to obtain optimal power allocation \mathbf{p}^* and interference pricing μ^* , with the input client set being S
 - 8: **if** $V_\varrho - \sum_{i \in S} p_i < 0$ **then**
 - 9: Stop iteration
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: Find the set of finally selected clients S^*
 - 13: Find ζ_i^* where $\zeta_i^* = 1\{i \in S^*\}$, $\mathbf{p}^* = \mathbf{p}^*(S^*)$ and $\mu^* = \mu^*(S^*)$
 - 14: Update energy queue according to (53)
-

information acquisition and lowers system complexity and operating costs.

- *Fairness:* Uniform pricing sets the same interference price for all IoMT clients, which avoids unfair situations that may be caused by information asymmetry and improves client acceptance.
- *Robustness:* In an environment with incomplete or inaccurate information, uniform pricing can provide a robust resource allocation mechanism that avoids the problem of resource allocation failure due to erroneous network state information.

V. ADAPTIVE POWER ALLOCATION AND CLIENT SELECTION IN LONG-TERM CONSIDERATIONS

In IoMT system, medical devices may not have a continuous energy supply. During FL training, if the energy cannot be allocated appropriately, the medical device will probably run out of battery energy before the FL training converges, which will make the FL performance degrade. Therefore, it is important to regulate the long-term energy as a whole. In previous sections, we discussed immediate power allocation and interference pricing for a given iteration. In this section, we further consider FL client selection strategies under long-term energy constraints. This requires optimization of the long-term FL performance metrics. Following the approach in [39], we introduce a performance metric for client i in round t , denoted as $U_i(t) = \zeta_i(t)\mathcal{D}_i\varrho(t)$. Here, $\zeta_i(t)$ is a binary variable indicating client i 's participation in round t , while $\varrho(t)$, an increasing sequence, underscores the improved FL performance with strategic client selection in later rounds. The objective encompasses maximizing the aggregated performance metric across all rounds and clients, subject to multiple

constraints

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max_{\zeta_i(t), p_i(t), \mu_i(t)} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i(t) \mathcal{D}_i \varrho(t) \\
\text{s.t. } & \sum_{i=1}^N I_i(p_i(t)) \leq C, \forall t, \\
& \mu_i(t) > 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall t, \\
& \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} \Lambda}{\sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} p_i(t))^2 + N_0}} \right)^2 \leq \mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta), \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \\
& r_i(p_i(t), \mathbf{p}_{-i}(t)) \geq \Lambda, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall t, \\
& 0 \leq p_i(t) \leq p^{max}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall t, \\
& \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i(t) p_i(t) \Delta_t \leq E_i^{max}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N},
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

where Δ_t is the granular time duration of one learning iteration, and E_i^{max} is the maximal energy budget of client i .

In the FL framework involving IoMT devices, the energy consumption for data processing and model training is large in each round of training. Including more clients in a given training round can improve the efficiency of the initial training. However, this approach may lead to a rapid exhaustion of the energy reserve of each client, which may prevent it from participating in future training rounds. Over time, this situation poses a risk to the continued efficiency and effectiveness of the FL process. To address this challenge, we employ a Lyapunov optimization technique to develop a virtual energy deficit queue for managing long-term energy consumption. Each client is initially set to zero, i.e., $q_i(0) = 0, \forall i$, and this queue is periodically updated to reflect each client's energy usage and remaining capacity with the following equation:

$$q_i(t+1) = [p_i(t) - E_i^{max}/T + q_i(t)]^+, \tag{53}$$

where $q_i(t)$ denotes the queue length of client i at time t , containing the gap between the energy consumed by the client in the current time interval and its allocated long-term energy ceiling. This virtual queue is a key tool for efficient management of energy resources during FL training.

Leveraging this framework, Algorithm 3 is designed to mitigate long-term energy constraints by intelligently selecting clients for participation in the FL process. The selection criterion is based on a priority metric, $\rho_i(t) \triangleq \frac{q_i(t)}{h_i(t)}$, which balances the energy queue length $q_i(t)$ with the channel state $h_i(t)$. This priority metric $\rho_i(t)$ reflects both the energy status and communication quality of each client. A lower $\rho_i(t)$ value indicates that the client has a higher channel gain and/or a lower energy queue, thereby making it a more favorable choice for participation. Clients with lower $\rho_i(t)$ values are prioritized to ensure a fair allocation of energy resources and to promote continuous engagement in the FL process. Subsequently, a sequential evaluation is performed to confirm that the inclusion of each client adheres to the operational constraints, thereby optimizing the FL process under energy limitations.

The complexity of Algorithm 3 is as follows. Lines 1, 2, 4, 12 to 14 are constant time operations. Line 3 involves sorting the clients, which has a complexity of $O(N \log N)$. The loop from lines 5 to 11 iterates up to N times, and within each iteration, either Algorithm 1 with complexity $O(N^2)$ or Algorithm 2 with complexity $O(T_1 N)$ is applied. Therefore, the loop's complexity is $O(N \cdot \max(N^2, T_1 N))$. Combining these, the total time complexity of Algorithm 3 is $O(N \log N + N^2 \cdot \max(N, T_1))$.

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To investigate the implementation of FL within the IoMT, we have designed a comprehensive experimental setup. This setup aims to assess the efficiency of our strategies for client selection, resource allocation, and privacy preservation under realistic IoMT conditions.

In our experimental network configuration, there is a single AP and server, with the total number of client devices N set at 20. These experiments are conducted within a wireless orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA) framework, which has a total bandwidth of 50 MHz, allocating $B = 5$ MHz for each channel. For parameter settings such as payoff factors λ_i , the maximum interference threshold from other clients β , and the background noise variance σ^2 , we align with the configurations suggested by [37]. We explore scenarios with different energy budgets for the clients: a sufficient energy condition with $E_i^{max} = 12$ J and a limited energy scenario with $E_i^{max} = 6$ J. Additionally, following the privacy parameter guidelines by [33], we set the fraction of power dedicated to generating artificial noise τ_i at 0.5.

We use the APTOS 2019 blindness detection dataset to train and evaluate our model [40]. This dataset has been widely used in research related to the diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy [41]–[43]. The dataset consists of 2931 variable-sized images for training and 731 images for testing, and all images are categorized into five classes based on the severity of diabetic retinopathy: No DR, Mild DR, Moderate DR, Severe DR, and Proliferative DR. To standardize the training process, we resized all images to a uniform size of 224×224 .

For the training process, we choose SqueezeNet [44], a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture designed to significantly reduce the number of parameters while achieving comparable accuracy to larger models like AlexNet. Specifically, SqueezeNet has 50x fewer parameters than AlexNet but maintains a similar accuracy on large datasets like ImageNet. The size of the model is an important consideration for both training and inference stages, especially when resources are limited, making the combination of the APTOS 2019 dataset and SqueezeNet particularly suitable for evaluating FL performance in resource-constrained FL IoMT scenarios [41].

A. Uniform and Non-Uniform Pricing

Our investigation into pricing strategies FL for the IoMT encompasses both uniform and non-uniform pricing models, as depicted in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b). These figures illustrate the AP utility and the sum-rate of clients as functions of the

Fig. 2. AP utility and sum-rate of clients vs. interference power constraint C . (a) AP utility vs. C . (b) Sum-rate of clients vs. C .

Fig. 3. Non-uniform pricing vs. uniform pricing. (a) Non-uniform interference price vs. C . (b) Uniform interference price vs. iterations.

interference constraint, C , under varying pricing strategies. When the interference constraint is low, the uniform pricing strategy yields higher AP utility and client sum-rate compared to the non-uniform approach. This is because uniform pricing applies a single interference price across all clients, which leads to a more balanced distribution of power. With a uniform price, each client adjusts its power allocation in the same way, preventing any one client from consuming too much of the limited interference budget. This straightforward allocation helps maximize sum-rate without requiring complex adjustments for each client, allowing the system to achieve better overall utility under tight constraints.

In contrast, non-uniform pricing assigns different interference prices to each client based on individual channel conditions. While this flexibility is beneficial in higher interference constraint environments, it is less effective in maximizing the sum-rate when the interference constraint is low. Non-uniform pricing gives priority to certain clients and often allocates more power to those with better channel conditions. However, this can lead to inefficient use of the interference constraint.

Further exploration, as shown in Fig. 3(a), focuses on the dynamics of optimal interference pricing across different clients under non-uniform pricing, in relation to the interference upper bound C . The channel gains of three of the clients satisfy the relationship:

$$\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1 B h_1}{g_1} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_1 A_1 + \beta + \sigma^2)}} < \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_2 B h_2}{g_2} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_2 A_2 + \beta + \sigma^2)}} < \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_3 B h_3}{g_3} \frac{\sqrt{\beta + \sigma^2}}{(h_3 A_3 + \beta + \sigma^2)}}.$$

In this case, for the same C , client 3 has the highest pricing. This is because client 3 can obtain a higher transmission rate while consuming the same amount of power, so client 3 is willing to pay a higher price. From Fig. 3(a), it can be seen that as C increases, the

Fig. 4. Sum-rate performance vs. C for different client numbers.

Fig. 5. Gap between the sum of interference from other clients and the interference upper bound β .

Fig. 6. Comparison of sum-rate of clients under different single iteration client selection methods.

price of interference to different clients generally decreases. In addition, the gap between the interference prices for different clients decreases. These phenomena are consistent with (43).

The performance of the distributed interference pricing algorithm (Algorithm 2) is critically examined in Fig. 3(b). The results affirm the algorithm's robustness, demonstrating convergence to the targeted precision across all examined C values. This finding underscores the efficacy of distributed approaches in dynamically adjusting interference prices to maintain network performance under varying resource availability conditions.

B. Scalability, Validation of Interference Assumption, and Comparative Analysis

In Fig. 4, we conduct a series of experiments to evaluate the performance of the framework with varying numbers of clients. The results show that the sum-rate performance improves as the interference power constraint increases, indicating a better utilization of power. The total sum-rate performance also improves as the number of clients increases. Specifically, the sum rate with 200 clients is significantly higher than that with 50 and 100 clients across all values of C . This shows that our framework can effectively scale to accommodate more clients while improving the overall performance of the system.

Fig. 5 illustrates the gap between the upper bound β and the sum of interference from other clients, $\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j$, under

Fig. 7. Comparison of test accuracy under different single iteration client selection methods.

varying interference power constraints C . The experiment is conducted with 200 clients. The results show that as the interference power constraint C increases, the total interference $\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j$ initially rises but then stabilizes. This indicates that the upper bound β is a reasonable estimate of the total interference received by client i from other clients j . Consequently, this experiment supports our model's assumption that $\sum_{j \neq i} \hat{p}_j h_j$ can be represented by the interference upper bound β .

In Fig. 6, we compare the client sum-rate of our proposed selection method (Algorithm 2) with that of the Greedy [29], MAB [30], and Random [31] methods in a single iteration. **Greedy:** It starts by assigning the same initial price to each client. It then calculates the immediate utility function for each client based on this pricing. Clients are sorted in descending order of their utility values, and within the interference constraint, clients are selected from highest to lowest utility value. **MAB:** It assigns the same initial price for each client and an ε value to balance exploration and exploitation. A random number between 0 and 1 is generated. If this number is less than ε , a random client is selected (exploration). Otherwise, the client with the highest current reward estimate (utility function) is chosen (exploitation). The reward estimate for the selected client is updated based on its actual performance. **Random:** It assigns the same initial price to each client and then randomly selects clients while ensuring that the total interference remains within the upper bound.

Across the entire range of interference constraints, our strategy consistently outperforms all baseline methods, demonstrating its superior ability to optimize client selection and power allocation. The advantage stems from the integration of the mathematical relationship between interference pricing and power allocation (specifically in Line 4 of Algorithm 2), which enables more efficient resource utilization based on the interference price. When the interference power constraint C is below 50 dB, our proposed strategy significantly outperforms the baseline methods. In this range, the baseline methods lack the adaptability to fully exploit the available interference budget, resulting in suboptimal resource allocation. As C

Fig. 8. Client selection dynamics across learning iterations. (a) Sufficient energy. (b) Limited energy.

increases beyond 50 dB, the performance differences among the baseline methods become more apparent. The Greedy method achieves relatively better performance by prioritizing immediate utility values, but its rigid selection approach limits its efficiency under relaxed constraints. The MAB method, which incorporates exploration and exploitation mechanisms, suffers from excessive randomness, leading to inefficient client selection and the lowest sum-rate performance among all methods in the 50-60 dB range. In contrast, the Random method, despite its simplicity, performs more stably than MAB in this range due to its uniform selection strategy.

In Fig. 7, we further evaluate the impact of different single iteration client selection strategies on test accuracy. As shown in the figure, Our strategy achieves higher and more stable test accuracy after the 100th learning iteration compared to the baseline methods, highlighting the advantages of our single iteration client selection approach. This improvement is due to our strategy's consideration of each client's channel properties and the mathematical relationship between pricing and power allocation. By incorporating these factors, our method enables more efficient power allocation, allowing for the selection of more clients within the interference constraint. In contrast, the baseline methods may result in less optimal power allocation, limiting the number of clients that can be selected while meeting the constraint, which ultimately leads to lower accuracy.

C. Long-Term Client Selection Subject to Energy Constraints

Inspired by [39], we use OCEAN-d as a baseline to explore the dynamics in the number of clients over long-term iterations. Unlike our approach, OCEAN-d employs a descending sequence for $\varrho(t)$, which tends to incorporate more clients in the initial phase of training and gradually reduces the number of participants as the training progresses. The two methods' impact on client selection across varying energy budgets is depicted in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b).

Fig. 8(a) illustrates the scenario with sufficient energy. Here, our strategy chooses a conservative approach in the initial phase, selecting fewer clients to reserve energy for later rounds. This contrasts with OCEAN-d, which selects many clients to participate in the early stages, thus limiting the ability to maintain client participation in the final stages of the training process. Our approach ensures a balanced distribution of participants across all training phases, demonstrating its effectiveness in managing energy resources more carefully.

Fig. 9. Comparison of test accuracy under different long-term client selection methods.

Fig. 8(b) illustrates a scenario with a limited energy budget. In the later phase of training, both strategies encountered challenges in maintaining client engagement due to energy shortages. Nonetheless, our approach maintains a high level of client engagement in the middle phase, which is attributed to the energy savings realized in the early phase. This highlights the ability of our approach to adapt and optimize client engagement under strict energy constraints.

In Fig. 9, we introduce two additional benchmarks from [39], OCEAN-a and OCEAN-u, to examine the effects of different long-term client selection strategies on test accuracy. Specifically, OCEAN-a selects a smaller number of clients in the initial learning iterations and gradually increases the client count as training progresses. OCEAN-u, under a total energy constraint, maintains an almost constant number of selected clients in each iteration.

As illustrated in Fig. 9, our strategy consistently achieves higher test accuracy than the baseline methods after the 100th learning iteration. The reasons why our strategy performs better than OCEAN-u and OCEAN-d are as follows. In the early stages of training, learning progress is not significantly affected even with a smaller number of clients. However, in the later stages, achieving higher accuracy requires contributions from a larger number of clients to provide more diverse updates to the global model. Therefore, our strategy dynamically adjusts to this need, utilizing more clients in the later stages to improve accuracy.

In contrast, OCEAN-a performs worse than our strategy for different reasons. OCEAN-a lacks an optimization mechanism for selecting clients in each iteration under interference constraints. Without specifically optimizing power allocation and client selection to comply with these constraints, OCEAN-a may fail to allocate power effectively, which reduces the number of clients that can be included within the constraints and ultimately impacts test accuracy.

D. Impact of Privacy Parameters on FL Performance

Regarding the effectiveness of our model in privacy preservation, we compare our approach with the standard FL method

Fig. 10. Comparison of test accuracy under different privacy-preserving methods.

Fig. 11. Comparison of attacker prediction accuracy under different privacy-preserving methods.

without privacy protection (FedAvg by [45]). In Fig. 10, we compare the test accuracy under different privacy-preserving methods and privacy parameter settings. In DP, ϵ quantifies the level of privacy leakage associated with the data used in learning. $\epsilon = 30$ indicates looser privacy controls, while $\epsilon = 20$ indicates stricter privacy controls. Our strategy is compared with a non-private FL method [45]. The experimental results show that a higher privacy budget ($\epsilon = 30$) allows for the use of more information in model training, thereby helping to maintain higher test accuracy.

To quantify the privacy preservation degree, we test our model as well as the comparison method using the inference attack method in [46]. Fig. 11 shows the attacker's prediction accuracy under different privacy-preserving methods. The results indicate that a higher privacy budget ($\epsilon = 30$) makes inference attacks easier as more information is used in model training. The results also show that our DP strategy significantly reduces the attacker's prediction accuracy, whereas the non-private FL performs poorly in defending against inference attacks. These experimental results illustrate the trade-offs between privacy protection and model accuracy.

Although using a differential privacy strategy may impact model accuracy to some extent, it significantly enhances the defense against inference attacks and improves overall privacy protection.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrates key improvements in FL in IoMT, focusing on securing health data while improving system accuracy and efficiency. By integrating DP and employing a game-theoretic approach to power allocation as well as strategic client selection, our approach achieves an optimal balance between data utility, network resource management, and energy and learning efficiency. We optimize communication resource allocation through a Stackelberg game model and adjust the power level of IoMT devices within the constraints of medical devices, resulting in efficient interference management through strategic pricing. To alleviate the energy constraints of IoMT devices, we employ a client selection strategy based on Lyapunov optimization to ensure that the devices continuously participate in FL while conserving energy. Our simulations confirm the effectiveness of our approach in improving the privacy, communication efficiency, and energy sustainability of IoMT FL systems. In the future, implementing our framework will require high-performance computing devices, upgraded network infrastructure, and privacy-preserving software support. We will also focus on integrating data integrity, adversarial defense strategies, and trust management to enhance system security and reliability. Additionally, exploring diverse network topologies and addressing device heterogeneity are key directions for future work.

APPENDIX

A. Proof of Lemma 1

In the proof, we first consider the case over a total of T iterations, and then divide the DP constraint equally among each iteration. The proof is similar to that of [36]. We denote $\mathbf{y}_i = [\mathbf{y}_i^1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_i^T]$ as the T successive received signals from IoMT device i , and $m_i^t = \sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t})^2 + N_0}$ is the standard deviation of the effective noise in \mathbf{y}_i^t . According to the definition of DP loss given in Definition 1, for the i -th device, the privacy loss after T iterations can be represented as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{D}'}(\mathbf{y}_i) &= \ln \left(\prod_{t=1}^T \frac{P[\mathbf{y}_i^t | \mathbf{y}_i^{t-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_i^1, \mathcal{D}_i]}{P[\mathbf{y}_i^t | \mathbf{y}_i^{t-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_i^1, \mathcal{D}'_i]} \right) \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^T \ln \left(\frac{P[\mathbf{y}_i^t | \mathbf{y}_i^{t-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_i^1, \mathcal{D}_i]}{P[\mathbf{y}_i^t | \mathbf{y}_i^{t-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_i^1, \mathcal{D}'_i]} \right) \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^T \ln \left(\frac{\exp \left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{y}_i^t - h_i^t \frac{\sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}}{\Lambda} \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}^t; \mathcal{D}_i)\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right)}{\exp \left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{y}_i^t - h_i^t \frac{\sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}}{\Lambda} \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}^t; \mathcal{D}'_i)\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^T \ln \left(\frac{\exp \left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_i^t\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right)}{\exp \left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_i^t + \mathbf{v}_i^t\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{r}_i^t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, (m_i^t)^2 \mathbf{I})$ represents the effective noise, and we set

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}_i^t &= h_i^t \frac{\sqrt{\theta_i p_i^t}}{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{(\mathbf{u}, v) \in \mathcal{D}_i} \nabla f(\mathbf{w}^t; \mathbf{u}, v) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \sum_{(\mathbf{u}, v) \in \mathcal{D}'_i} \nabla f(\mathbf{w}^t; \mathbf{u}, v) \right], \end{aligned}$$

where $\|\mathbf{v}_i^t\| = \Delta_i^t$. Following the conclusion in [35], we can then bound privacy violation probability

$$\begin{aligned} &\Pr \left(\left| \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{2(\mathbf{r}_i^t)^\top \mathbf{v}_i^t + \|\mathbf{v}_i^t\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right| > \epsilon \right) \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\leq} \Pr \left(\left| \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(\mathbf{r}_i^t)^\top \mathbf{v}_i^t}{(m_i^t)^2} \right| > \epsilon - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_i^t\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right) \\ &= 2 \Pr \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(\mathbf{r}_i^t)^\top \mathbf{v}_i^t}{(m_i^t)^2} > \epsilon - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_i^t\|^2}{2(m_i^t)^2} \right) \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{\leq} 2 \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2}}{\sqrt{2\pi} \left[\epsilon - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2 \right]} \\ &\quad \times \exp \left(-\frac{\left[\epsilon - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2 \right]^2}{2 \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where (a) is obtained by using $\Pr(X < -\epsilon - b) \leq \Pr(X < -\epsilon + b)$ for an arbitrary $b \geq 0$, and (b) comes from the distribution

$$\begin{aligned} X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2) : \Pr(X > s) &= \frac{1}{\sigma \sqrt{2\pi}} \int_s^\infty \exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) dx \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\sigma \sqrt{2\pi}} \int_s^\infty \frac{x}{s} \exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) dx \\ &= \frac{\sigma}{s \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left(-\frac{s^2}{2\sigma^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Letting $q = \frac{\epsilon - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2}{\sqrt{2 \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{\Delta_i^t}{m_i^t} \right)^2}}$, the DP condition is implied by the inequality

$$\Pr(|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{D}'}(\mathbf{y}_i)| > \epsilon) \leq \frac{1}{q\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-q^2} < \delta.$$

Finally, defining the function $C(x) = \sqrt{\pi} x e^{x^2}$ and utilizing its monotonicity yields the result

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} \Lambda}{m_k^{(t)}} \right)^2 &\leq \left(\sqrt{\epsilon + [C^{-1}(1/\delta)]^2} - C^{-1}(1/\delta) \right)^2 \\ &\triangleq \mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta). \end{aligned}$$

To simplify the subsequent analyses, we divide the DP constraints equally into each iteration, thus obtaining the desired result

$$\left(\frac{\sqrt{2} h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} \Lambda}{\sqrt{(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i} p_i)^2 + N_0}} \right)^2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{R}_{\text{dp}}(\epsilon, \delta)}{T}.$$

B. Proof of Lemma 2

For the convergence analysis of FL, we refer to [36] and follow the assumptions about the loss function in [36].

Under Assumption 1, we have the following equality

$$\begin{aligned}
F(\mathbf{w}^{(t)}) &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) + \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right]^\top \left[\mathbf{w}^{(t)} - \mathbf{w}^{(t-1)} \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{L}{2} \left\| \mathbf{w}^{(t)} - \mathbf{w}^{(t-1)} \right\|^2 \\
&= F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) - \eta \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right]^\top \times \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\mathbf{n}_i^{(t-1)} + \left(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^t} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{z}_i^{(t-1)} \right] \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{L\eta^2}{2} \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right\|^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \mathbf{n}_i^{(t-1)} + \left(h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^{(t-1)}} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{z}_i^{(t-1)} \right\|^2.
\end{aligned}$$

By taking the expectation of the noise $\mathbf{n}_i^{(t-1)}$ and $\mathbf{z}_i^{(t-1)}$ on both sides of the above inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} \left[F(\mathbf{w}^{(t)}) \right] &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) - \eta \left[\left(1 - \frac{L\eta}{2} \right) \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right\|^2 \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{L\eta^2}{2N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left((1)^2 + \left(\frac{\sqrt{N_0}}{h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^{(t-1)}}} \right)^2 \right) \\
&= F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) - \frac{1}{2L} \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right\|^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2LN^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{m_i^{(t-1)}}{h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^{(t-1)}}} \right)^2,
\end{aligned}$$

where the equality follows by setting $\eta = \frac{1}{L}$.

Subtracting F^* from both sides and applying Assumption 2, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} \left[F(\mathbf{w}^{(t)}) \right] - F^* &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) - F^* - \frac{1}{2L} \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) \right\|^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2LN^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{m_i^{(t-1)}}{h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^{(t-1)}}} \right)^2 \\
&\leq \left(1 - \frac{\psi}{L} \right) \left(F(\mathbf{w}^{(t-1)}) - F^* \right) + \frac{1}{2LN^2} \\
&\quad \times \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{m_i^{(t-1)}}{h_i \sqrt{\tau_i p_i^{(t-1)}}} \right)^2,
\end{aligned}$$

The final result for Lemma 2 can be obtained by repeatedly using this inequality in T iterations and taking an expectation over the noise \mathbf{n}_i and \mathbf{z}_i .

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